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A DIAGNOSTIC DECISION MODEL BASED ON VAGUE SETS

D. PANDEY, KAMESH KUMAR, AND M. K. SHARMA

ABSTRACT. Medical diagnosis involves various kinds of uncertainties in the process. This makes the diagnostic decision analysis an important platform for the applicability of fuzzy sets. Some researchers have given a fuzzy decision making model for medical diagnosis based on fuzzy numbers and compositional rule. Fuzzy set theoretic analysis is usually centered on the choice of proper membership grades for the elements of fuzzy sets. A single value for the membership grade based on the combined effect of favourable and unfavourable evidence, does not speak much about the appropriateness. Vague set theory takes into account the favourable and unfavourable evidence separately and provides a closed interval in which the membership grade may lie. This paper defines triangular vague numbers to extend the concept of triangular fuzzy numbers and generalizes the model of Yao and Yao using vague set theory. Application of this method to their example covers up the vagueness in the symptom disease relationship and the lack of specificity in patient-symptom observations in a more realistic manner and increases the credibility of the diagnostic decision.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fuzzy set theory proposed by Zadeh [10] permits the replacement of sharp boundaries in classical set theory by fuzzy boundaries. The concept of belongingness of an element in the context of classical sets changes to membership grade of the element to certain degree in fuzzy sets. The membership grade of an element x of the fuzzy set is given by a real number between zero and one. Due to fuzzy boundaries, this single value for the membership grade is the result of the combined effect of evidence in favour and against the inclusion of the element in the set [1]. The utility of the application of fuzzy sets depends on the capability of the user to construct appropriate membership functions, which are often very precise. In

Keywords and phrases: vague set, lower and upper membership functions, vague point, triangular vague number

ISSN 0019 - 5839

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many contexts it is difficult to assign a particular real number as a membership grade and in such cases it may be useful to identify meaningful lower and upper bounds for the membership grade. Such generalization of fuzzy sets, called interval-valued fuzzy sets has already been used for Sanchez approach to medical diagnosis [7].

Concept of vague sets given by Gau and Buehrer [3] takes into account the favourable and unfavourable evidence separately providing a lower and an upper bound within which the membership grade may lie. The membership grade of an element x in a vague set is represented by a vague value [1] $[\mu_x, 1 - \nu_x] \subseteq [0, 1]$, where μ_x indicates the degree of truth, ν_x represents the degree of falsity and $(1 - \mu_x - \nu_x)$ the unknown part, $0 \leq \mu_x \leq 1 - \nu_x \leq 1$ and $\mu_x + \nu_x \leq 1$. Vague sets are higher order fuzzy sets [5] which are capable of providing more realistic results. A vague set reduces to the fuzzy set if $\mu_x = 1 - \nu_x$. The application of fuzzy sets is quite useful in decision making when the decisions are to be made under vague and nonspecific situations [11]. Chen and Tan [2], Hong and Choi [4] applied vague set theory to multicriteria fuzzy decision problems. Medicine is a field in which the applicability of fuzzy sets was recognized quite early due to the uncertainties involved in the process of diagnosis of disease. A single symptom may be indicative of more than one disease and many diseases in a single patient may disrupt the expected symptom pattern of any one of them [6]. The gravity of the diagnostic problem further increases due to the fact that the data cannot be assigned relative weights to appropriately represent their degree of relevance in the decision process. In the face of uncertainty concerning the observed symptoms of the patient and also the uncertainty concerning the relation of symptom to disease, the diagnostic decision becomes crucial and needs more attention to deal with the vagueness and nonspecificity. Yao and Yao [9] have given a fuzzy decision making model for medical diagnosis based on fuzzy numbers and compositional rule. We define triangular vague numbers to extend the concept of triangular fuzzy numbers and generalize their model using vague set theory. In this paper, a decision making model for medical diagnosis using vague sets, is proposed. Medical knowledge of the experts has been used to represent the role of the symptoms in the diseases. Vague matrices have been used to represent the relationship between patients and symptoms and symptoms and diseases. These matrices are determined through statistical method. The case studied in [9] has also been

worked out through this approach. Our methodology is more flexible than [9] because it takes into consideration the unfavourable aspects also.

2. BASIC CONCEPTS OF VAGUE SETS

Vague set. A vague set \bar{A} in the universe of discourse X is characterized by a membership $\mu_{\bar{A}} : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and a non-membership function $\nu_{\bar{A}} : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$. The grade of membership for any element x in the vague set is bounded by a sub interval $[\mu_{\bar{A}}(x), 1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x)]$, where the grade $\mu_{\bar{A}}(x)$ is called lower bound of membership grade of x derived from evidences for x and $\nu_{\bar{A}}(x)$ is the lower bound of membership grade on the negation of x derived from the evidences against x and $\mu_{\bar{A}}(x) + \nu_{\bar{A}}(x) \leq 1$. In the extreme case of equality $\mu_{\bar{A}}(x) = 1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x)$, the vague set reduces to the fuzzy set with interval value of the membership grade reducing to a single value $\mu_{\bar{A}}(x)$. In general, however,

$$\mu_{\bar{A}}(x) \leq \text{exact membership grade of } x \leq 1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x).$$

Expressions given below can be used to represent a vague set \bar{A} for finite, denumerable and uncountable universe of discourse X respectively.

$$\bar{A} = \sum_{k=1}^n [\mu_{\bar{A}}(x_k), 1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x_k)]/x_k, \quad \bar{A} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [\mu_{\bar{A}}(x_k), 1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x_k)]/x_k,$$

$$\bar{A} = \int_{x \in X} [\mu_{\bar{A}}(x), 1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x)]/x.$$

A vague set is represented pictorially as

The concept of vague number [1] is introduced in the following.

Convex vague set. Let \bar{A} be a vague set of the universe of discourse X with $\mu_{\bar{A}}$ and $\nu_{\bar{A}}$ as its membership and non-membership functions respectively. The vague set is convex if and only if for every pair of $x_1, x_2 \in X$

there is

$$\mu_{\bar{A}}(\lambda x_1 + (1 - \lambda)x_2) \geq \text{Min}(\mu_{\bar{A}}(x_1), \mu_{\bar{A}}(x_2)) \text{ and}$$

$$1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(\lambda x_1 + (1 - \lambda)x_2) \geq \text{Min}(1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x_1), 1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x_2)) \text{ where } \lambda \in [0, 1].$$

Normal vague set. A vague set \bar{A} in the universe of discourse X is called normal if $\exists x_i \in X$, such that $1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x_i) = 1$, i.e., $\nu_{\bar{A}}(x_i) = 0$.

Vague number. A vague number is a vague set in the universe of the discourse X that is both convex and normal.

3. TRIANGULAR VAGUE NUMBER

Chen [1] defined triangular vague sets and arithmetic operations between them. On the similar lines, we introduce the concept of a triangular vague number.

A triangular vague number \bar{A} denoted by $[(a, b, c); k; 1]$ is characterized by a pair of membership functions: a lower membership function.

$$(3.1) \quad \mu_{\bar{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{k(x-a)}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b \\ \frac{k(c-x)}{c-b}, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

and an upper membership function

$$(3.2) \quad \mu'_{\bar{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-a}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b}, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $\mu'_{\bar{A}}(x) = 1 - \nu_{\bar{A}}(x)$ and $k \in [0, 1]$. Fig- 2 shows a triangular vague number

Fig-2

When $k = 1$, triangular vague number reduces to a triangular fuzzy number. In what follows now onwards, we shall use vague number for a

triangular vague number.

Vague point. In a triangular vague number $\bar{A} = [(a, b, c); k; 1]$, if $a = c = b$, then $\bar{A} = b_k = [(b, b, b); k; 1]$ is said to be a vague point. A vague point b_k reduces to a fuzzy point b_1 for $k = 1$.

Centroid of vague number. Centroid $C_{\bar{A}}$ of a vague number $[(a, b, c); k; 1]$, is

$$C_{\bar{A}} = \begin{cases} \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(\mu_{\bar{A}}(x) - \mu'_{\bar{A}}(x))dx}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\mu_{\bar{A}}(x) - \mu'_{\bar{A}}(x))dx} & \text{for } k \in (0, 1); \\ \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x\mu_{\bar{A}}(x)dx}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mu_{\bar{A}}(x)dx} & \text{for } k = 1 \end{cases}$$

Using $\mu_{\bar{A}}(x)$ and $\mu'_{\bar{A}}(x)$ as given in (3.1) and (3.2) and computing the values of the integrals, it is easy to verify for every value of $k \in [0, 1]$ that

$$(3.3) \quad C_{\bar{A}} = \frac{1}{3}(a + b + c)$$

Let $V_N(k) = \{[(a, b, c); k; 1] : a < b < c, a, b, c \in R\}$, $V_p(k) = \{[(b, b, b); k; 1] : b \in R, k \in [0, 1]\}$ be the sets of vague numbers and vague points respectively. Further let V_N denotes a set of vague numbers for any k . Clearly, $F_p(1) \subset V_p(k)$, where $F_p(1) = \{[(b, b, b); 1; 1] : b \in R\}$ is the set of fuzzy points [9].

The operations \oplus and \otimes can be defined for vague numbers in a manner similar to vague sets [1].

$$(3.4) \quad [(a_1, b_1, c_1); k_1; 1] \oplus [(a_2, b_2, c_2); k_2; 1] = [(a_1 + a_2, b_1 + b_2, c_1 + c_2); \text{Min}(k_1, k_2); 1].$$

$$(3.5) \quad [(a_1, b_1, c_1); k_1; 1] \otimes [(a_2, b_2, c_2); k_2; 1] = [(a_1 a_2, b_1 b_2, c_1 c_2); \text{Min}(k_1, k_2); 1].$$

Property 1. If $\bar{A}, \bar{B} \in V_N(k) \& \bar{I}_k, \bar{m}_k, \bar{n}_k \in V_p(k)$, then

- (i) $\bar{I}_k \oplus \bar{m}_k = (\bar{I} + \bar{m})_k, \bar{I}_k \otimes \bar{m}_k = (\bar{I}\bar{m})_k$.
- (ii) If $\bar{A}_k = [(a_1, b_1, c_1); k; 1], \bar{B} = [(a_2, b_2, c_2); k; 1]$ then $\bar{A} \oplus \bar{B} = [(a_1 + a_2 b_1 + b_2 c_1 + c_1); k; 1]$.
- (iii) If $\bar{A} = [(a, b, c); k; 1]$ then $\bar{I}_k \otimes \bar{A} = \begin{cases} [(la, lb, lc); k; 1] & \text{for } l > 0 \\ [(0, 0, 0); k; 1] & \text{for } l < 0. \end{cases}$

Proof Using (3.4) and (3.5), proof is obvious.

Signed distance between two vague sets

A vague set \tilde{A} has two membership functions, a lower function \tilde{A}_L and an upper one \tilde{A}_U . Correspondingly it has two α -cuts,

$$(3.6) \quad \tilde{A}_L = [a + \frac{1}{k}(b-a)\alpha, c - \frac{1}{k}(c-b)\alpha] = [\tilde{A}_L^l, \tilde{A}_L^r] \text{ and}$$

$$(3.7) \quad \tilde{A}_U = [a + (b-a)\alpha, c - (c-b)\alpha] = [\tilde{A}_U^l, \tilde{A}_U^r].$$

Definition 3.1. *The signed distance between two vague numbers $\tilde{A} = [(a_1, b_1, c_1); k_1; 1]$ and $\tilde{B} = [(a_2, b_2, c_2); k_2; 1]$ is defined as:*

$$(3.8) \quad d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_0^1 \left(\frac{\tilde{A}_U^l(\alpha) + \tilde{A}_U^r(\alpha)}{2} - \frac{\tilde{B}_U^l(\alpha) + \tilde{B}_U^r(\alpha)}{2} \right) d\alpha + \frac{1}{k_1} \int_0^{k_1} \left(\frac{\tilde{A}_L^l(\alpha) + \tilde{A}_L^r(\alpha)}{2} \right) d\alpha - \frac{1}{k_2} \int_0^{k_2} \left(\frac{\tilde{B}_L^l(\alpha) + \tilde{B}_L^r(\alpha)}{2} \right) d\alpha \right].$$

Using (3.6) and (3.7), we get

$$(3.9) \quad d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) = \frac{1}{4}(2b_1 + a_1 + c_1 - 2b_2 + a_2 + c_2).$$

Equation (3.8) reduces to the expression given in Definition 3 [9] for $k_1 = k_2 = 1$. It is clear from (3.9) that distance between two vague numbers is independent of k , thus it has same value for the corresponding fuzzy numbers.

Property 2. If $\tilde{A} = [(a_1, b_1, c_1); k; 1]$, $\tilde{B} = [(a_2, b_2, c_2); k; 1] \in V_N$, $\tilde{0}_k = [(0, 0, 0); k; 1] \in V_p(k)$, then

$$(3.10) \quad d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{0}_k) = \frac{1}{4}(2b_1 + a_1 + c_1),$$

$$(3.11) \quad d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) = d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{0}_k) - d(\tilde{B}, \tilde{0}_k).$$

Proof of (3.10). Setting $\tilde{B} = \tilde{0}_k$, in (3.8) and substituting for \tilde{A}_U^l , \tilde{A}_U^r , \tilde{A}_L^l and \tilde{A}_L^r from (3.6) and (3.7), the result follows.

Proof of (3.11). Using (3.9) and (3.10) result is obvious.

Definition 3.2. For $\tilde{A}, \tilde{B} \in V_N$ we can define the following ordering for vague sets on V_N in a manner similar to fuzzy sets.

$$\tilde{A} \succ \tilde{B} \Leftrightarrow d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) > 0 \Leftrightarrow d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{0}_k) > d(\tilde{B}, \tilde{0}_k),$$

$$\tilde{A} \approx \tilde{B} \Leftrightarrow d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) = 0 \Leftrightarrow d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{0}_k) = d(\tilde{B}, \tilde{0}_k),$$

$$\tilde{A} \prec \tilde{B} \Leftrightarrow d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) < 0 \Leftrightarrow d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{0}_k) < d(\tilde{B}, \tilde{0}_k).$$

4. DECISION MAKING FOR MEDICAL DIAGNOSIS

4.1. **Method I (Using vague sets).** Let $S = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n\}$, $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_l\}$ and $D = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_m\}$ be the crisp sets of symptoms, patients and diseases respectively. In vague set theory we need two fuzzy relations called membership relation (\tilde{R}_L) representing the lower bound and non-membership relation (\tilde{R}_N) contributing towards the upper bound, to derive the relationship between the set of symptoms and set of diseases. Let the fuzzy relations (\tilde{R}_L) and (\tilde{R}_N) between S and D be expressed as following:

$$(4.1) \quad \tilde{R}_L = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & \cdot & \cdot & r_{1m} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & \cdot & \cdot & r_{2m} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ r_{n1} & r_{n2} & \cdot & \cdot & r_{nm} \end{bmatrix} \quad \tilde{R}_N = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & \cdot & \cdot & c_{1m} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & \cdot & \cdot & c_{2m} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ c_{n1} & c_{n2} & \cdot & \cdot & c_{nm} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Substituting $r'_{ij} = 1 - c_{ij}$; for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, m$, in \tilde{R}_N we get the upper bound of the membership relation (upper membership relation) \tilde{R}_U

$$(4.2) \quad \tilde{R}_U = \begin{bmatrix} r'_{11} & r'_{12} & \cdot & \cdot & r'_{1m} \\ r'_{21} & r'_{22} & \cdot & \cdot & r'_{2m} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ r'_{n1} & r'_{n2} & \cdot & \cdot & r'_{nm} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The vague membership relations between patients and symptoms, that is, \tilde{A}_L and \tilde{A}_U can be obtained similar to \tilde{R}_L and \tilde{R}_U :

$$(4.3) \quad \tilde{A}_L = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdot & \cdot & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdot & \cdot & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_{l1} & a_{l2} & \cdot & \cdot & a_{ln} \end{bmatrix} \quad \tilde{A}_U = \begin{bmatrix} a'_{11} & a'_{12} & \cdot & \cdot & a'_{1n} \\ a'_{21} & a'_{22} & \cdot & \cdot & a'_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ a'_{l1} & a'_{l2} & \cdot & \cdot & a'_{ln} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Determination of r_{ij}, r'_{ij}, a_{ij} and a'_{ij} . Let N be the number of past patients on whom the statistical estimation is based. We also use following notations.

N_i : Number of cases having symptom S_i ,
 N'_i : Number of cases not having symptom S_i ,
 N_{ij} : Number of patients having symptom S_i with diagnosis in favour of disease d_j

$(i = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, m)$; and $\sum_{j=1}^m N_{ij} = N_i$, for each i .

N'_{ij} : Number of patients not having symptom S_i but having diagnosis in favour of disease d_j ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, m$); $\sum_{j=1}^m N'_{ij} = N'_i$ for each i . r_{ij} and r'_{ij} can now be determined by the following expressions:

$r_{ij} = \frac{N_{ij}}{N_i}$ and $r'_{ij} = 1 - c_{ij}$, where $c_{ij} = \frac{N'_{ij}}{N'_i}$. We also have $\sum_{j=1}^m r_{ij} = 1$ and $\sum_{j=1}^m c_{ij} = 1$ for each $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. a_{ij} and a'_{ij} are determined by physician's diagnosis.

We now need a relation between the set of patients and the set of diseases to facilitate the diagnosis of the disease in the patients. The vague relation \tilde{T} between the sets P and D includes two fuzzy relations $\tilde{T}_L = \tilde{A}_L \circ \tilde{R}_L$ and $\tilde{T}_U = \tilde{A}_U \circ \tilde{R}_U$, that can be obtained using composition rule of inference:

$$(4.4) \quad \tilde{T}_L = \begin{bmatrix} t_{11} & t_{12} & \cdot & \cdot & t_{1m} \\ t_{21} & t_{22} & \cdot & \cdot & t_{2m} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ t_{l1} & t_{l2} & \cdot & \cdot & t_{lm} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{T}_U = \begin{bmatrix} t'_{11} & t'_{12} & \cdot & \cdot & t'_{1m} \\ t'_{21} & t'_{22} & \cdot & \cdot & t'_{2m} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ t'_{l1} & t'_{l2} & \cdot & \cdot & t'_{lm} \end{bmatrix}.$$

To obtain the elements of \tilde{T}_L we may use any of the following two composition rules:

$$(4.5) \quad t_{ij} = \max_h [\min(a_{ih}, r_{hj})],$$

$$(4.6) \quad t_{ij} = \min \left[\sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih}, r_{hj}, 1 \right]$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, l$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Composition rule for the elements t'_{ij} of \tilde{T}_U can be obtained by replacing a_{ih} and r_{hj} in (4.5) and (4.6) by a'_{ih} and r'_{hj} respectively.

In the fuzzy set theoretic approach $\tilde{T}_L = \tilde{T}_U = \tilde{T}$, hence the diagnostic decision is based only on a single relation \tilde{T} between the patients and diseases. In vague set theory \tilde{T}_L represents the relationship between the patients and the diseases on the basis of favourable evidences while \tilde{T}_U gives same relationship based on unfavourable evidences. Thus \tilde{T}_L may

not necessarily be same as \tilde{T}_U . It is therefore necessary to use some aggregation operation to combine \tilde{T}_L and \tilde{T}_U to get a single relation \tilde{T} between symptoms and diseases whose membership grades are based on due considerations to favourable and unfavourable evidences. The aggregation through intersection and union operators give the lower and upper bounds for the membership grades respectively while the averaging operator gives a mid-value within the bounds. We prefer to use the later approach on the normalized forms of \tilde{T}_L and \tilde{T}_U .

$$(4.7) \quad \tilde{T}^* = \frac{1}{2}(\tilde{T}_L^* + \tilde{T}_U^*) = \begin{bmatrix} t_{11}^* & t_{12}^* & \cdot & \cdot & t_{1m}^* \\ t_{21}^* & t_{22}^* & \cdot & \cdot & t_{2m}^* \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ t_{l1}^* & t_{l2}^* & \cdot & \cdot & t_{lm}^* \end{bmatrix}$$

where \tilde{T}_L^* and \tilde{T}_U^* are the normalized forms of \tilde{T}_L and \tilde{T}_U respectively. Using probability distribution rule [9], each t_{ij}^* in \tilde{T}^* gives the expected percentage of presence of disease d_j in patient P_i . Further if $\max_{i \leq h \leq m} t_{ih}^* = t_{ij}^*$, then patient P_i 's diagnosis can be given as d_j .

Remark. An alternative approach to such diagnostic decision can be worked out using Dempster-Shafer theory of evidence. In this case, the symptoms will work as evidence. Basic probability assignment for possible diseases may be obtained through expert opinion. Dempster-Shafer rule of combination can then be used on this data to have joint basic assignment [6]. Belief and plausibility measures can now be computed to infer the disease [8].

4.2. Method II (Using triangular vague numbers). Earlier in this paper we obtained statistical point estimates of r_{ij} and r'_{ij} . Following Yao and Yao [9, p 354] we obtain interval estimates for r_{ij} and $r'_{ij} (= 1 - c_{ij})$ at 99% confidence level:

$$(4.8) \quad [r_{ij}^{(1)}, r_{ij}^{(2)}] = \left[r_{ij} - 2.575 \sqrt{\frac{r_{ij}(1-r_{ij})}{N_i}}, r_{ij} + 2.575 \sqrt{\frac{r_{ij}(1-r_{ij})}{N_i}} \right],$$

$$[c_{ij}^{(1)}, c_{ij}^{(2)}] = \left[c_{ij} - 2.575 \sqrt{\frac{c_{ij}(1-c_{ij})}{N'_i}}, c_{ij} + 2.575 \sqrt{\frac{c_{ij}(1-c_{ij})}{N'_i}} \right],$$

$$(4.9) \quad [r_{ij}^{i(1)}, r_{ij}^{i(2)}] = [1 - c_{ij}^{(1)}, 1 - c_{ij}^{(2)}].$$

Using (4.8) and (4.9), two triangular vague numbers \tilde{r}_{ij} and \tilde{r}'_{ij} (representing lower and upper memberships) as following:

$$(4.10) \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{r}_{ij} &= \left[(r_{ij}^{(1)}, r_{ij}, r_{ij}^{(2)}); k_{ij}; 1 \right], \\ \tilde{r}'_{ij} &= \left[(r'_{ij}{}^{(1)}, r'_{ij}, r'_{ij}{}^{(2)}); k'_{ij}; 1 \right], \end{aligned}$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Property 3. For vague numbers, \tilde{r}_{ij} and \tilde{r}'_{ij} as given in (4.10), we have following properties:

- (i) the centroid of $\tilde{r}_{ij}(C_{\tilde{r}_{ij}}) = r_{ij}$, (ii) the centroid of $\tilde{r}'_{ij}(C_{\tilde{r}'_{ij}}) = r'_{ij}$
 (iii) $d(\tilde{r}_{ij}, \tilde{0}_k) = r_{ij} = C_{r_{ij}}$ (iv) $d(\tilde{r}'_{ij}, \tilde{0}_k) = r'_{ij} = C_{r'_{ij}}$.

Proof. It is similar to the proof for a fuzzy number [9, p356].

For deriving a method of diagnostic decision, based on vague numbers, we replace the matrices \tilde{R}_L and \tilde{R}_U given in (4.1) and (4.2) by vague matrices, that is, matrices having vague numbers as elements. Let \tilde{R}_L^* and \tilde{R}_U^* given below, denote the replaced matrices, where the elements \tilde{r}_{ij} and \tilde{r}'_{ij} are given by (4.10).

$$(4.11) \quad \tilde{R}_L^* = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{r}_{11} & \tilde{r}_{12} & \cdot & \tilde{r}_{1m} \\ \tilde{r}_{21} & \tilde{r}_{22} & \cdot & \tilde{r}_{2m} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \tilde{r}_{n1} & \tilde{r}_{n2} & \cdot & \tilde{r}_{nm} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{R}_U^* = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{r}'_{11} & \tilde{r}'_{12} & \cdot & \tilde{r}'_{1m} \\ \tilde{r}'_{21} & \tilde{r}'_{22} & \cdot & \tilde{r}'_{2m} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \tilde{r}'_{n1} & \tilde{r}'_{n2} & \cdot & \tilde{r}'_{nm} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Vague matrices \tilde{A}_L^* and \tilde{A}_U^* will now be used in place of \tilde{A}_L and \tilde{A}_U . Using (4.3) we can define \tilde{A}_L^* and \tilde{A}_U^* as following:

$$(4.12) \quad \tilde{A}_L^* = \begin{bmatrix} (a_{11})_k & (a_{12})_k & \cdot & \cdot & (a_{1n})_k \\ (a_{21})_k & (a_{22})_k & \cdot & \cdot & (a_{2n})_k \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ (a_{l1})_k & (a_{l2})_k & \cdot & \cdot & (a_{ln})_k \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{A}_U^* = \begin{bmatrix} (a'_{11})_k & (a'_{12})_k & \cdot & \cdot & (a'_{1n})_k \\ (a'_{21})_k & (a'_{22})_k & \cdot & \cdot & (a'_{2n})_k \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ (a'_{l1})_k & (a'_{l2})_k & \cdot & \cdot & (a'_{ln})_k \end{bmatrix}$$

where $(a_{ij})_k = [(a_{ij}, a_{ij}, a_{ij}); k; 1] \in V_p(k)$ and $(a'_{ij})_k = [(a'_{ij}, a'_{ij}, a'_{ij}); k; 1] \in V_p(k)$.

We use following composition rules to determine vague relations \tilde{T}_L^* and \tilde{T}_U^* :

$$(4.13) \quad \tilde{t}_{ij}^* = ((a_{i1})_k \otimes \tilde{r}_{1j}) \oplus ((a_{i2})_k \otimes \tilde{r}_{2j}) \oplus \dots \oplus ((a_{in})_k \otimes \tilde{r}_{nj});$$

$$(4.14) \quad \tilde{t}'_{ij}^* = ((a'_{i1})_k \otimes \tilde{r}'_{1j}) \oplus ((a'_{i2})_k \otimes \tilde{r}'_{2j}) \oplus \dots \oplus ((a'_{in})_k \otimes \tilde{r}'_{nj}),$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, l$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. From (4.11), (4.12) and above mentioned composition rules we get:

$$(4.15) \quad \tilde{T}_L^* = \tilde{A}_L^* \circ \tilde{R}_L^* = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{t}_{11}^* & \tilde{t}_{12}^* & \cdot & \tilde{t}_{1m}^* \\ \tilde{t}_{21}^* & \tilde{t}_{22}^* & \cdot & \tilde{t}_{2m}^* \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \tilde{t}_{l1}^* & \tilde{t}_{l2}^* & \cdot & \tilde{t}_{lm}^* \end{bmatrix},$$

$$(4.16) \quad \tilde{T}_U^* = \tilde{A}_U^* \circ \tilde{R}_U^* = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{t}'_{11}^* & \tilde{t}'_{12}^* & \cdot & \tilde{t}'_{1m}^* \\ \tilde{t}'_{21}^* & \tilde{t}'_{22}^* & \cdot & \tilde{t}'_{2m}^* \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \tilde{t}'_{l1}^* & \tilde{t}'_{l2}^* & \cdot & \tilde{t}'_{lm}^* \end{bmatrix}.$$

By property 1(ii), (iii) and equations (4.13), (4.14) we get

$$(4.17) \quad \tilde{t}_{ij}^* = \left[\left(\sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}^{(1)}, \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}, \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}^{(2)} \right); \min(k, \min_{1 \leq h \leq n} k_{hj}); 1 \right],$$

$$(4.18) \quad \tilde{t}'_{ij}^* = \left[\left(\sum_{h=1}^n a'_{ih} r'_{hj}{}^{(1)}, \sum_{h=1}^n a'_{ih} r'_{hj}, \sum_{h=1}^n a'_{ih} r'_{hj}{}^{(2)} \right); \min(k, \min_{1 \leq h \leq n} k'_{hj}); 1 \right].$$

Property 4. For \tilde{t}_{ij}^* and \tilde{t}'_{ij}^* given by (4.17) and (4.18)

$$(i) C_{t_{ij}^*} = d(\tilde{t}_{ij}^*, \tilde{0}_{ij}) = \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}, \quad (ii) C_{t'_{ij}^*} = d(\tilde{t}'_{ij}^*, \tilde{0}_{ij}) = \sum_{h=1}^n a'_{ih} r'_{hj}.$$

Proof of (i). Since the centroid of a vague number $[(a, b, c); k; 1]$ can be given by $C_{\tilde{A}} = \frac{1}{3}(a + b + c)$ in (3.3), we have

$$C_{\tilde{t}_{ij}^*} = \frac{1}{3} \left\{ \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}^{(1)} + \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj} + \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}^{(2)} \right\} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} (3r_{hj}) = \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}.$$

Further using Property 2(i)

$$\begin{aligned} d(\tilde{t}_{ij}^*, \tilde{0}_{ij}) &= \frac{1}{4} \left\{ \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}^{(1)} + 2 \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj} + \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}^{(2)} \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{4} \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} (4r_{hj}) = \sum_{h=1}^n a_{ih} r_{hj}. \end{aligned}$$

Property 4(ii) can be proved in a similar manner.

Now, define

$$(4.19) \quad D_L = \begin{bmatrix} d(\tilde{t}_{11}^*, \tilde{0}_{11}) & d(\tilde{t}_{12}^*, \tilde{0}_{12}) & \cdot & \cdot & d(\tilde{t}_{1m}^*, \tilde{0}_{1m}) \\ d(\tilde{t}_{21}^*, \tilde{0}_{21}) & d(\tilde{t}_{22}^*, \tilde{0}_{22}) & \cdot & \cdot & d(\tilde{t}_{2m}^*, \tilde{0}_{2m}) \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ d(\tilde{t}_{l1}^*, \tilde{0}_{l1}) & d(\tilde{t}_{l2}^*, \tilde{0}_{l2}) & \cdot & \cdot & d(\tilde{t}_{lm}^*, \tilde{0}_{lm}) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= [d(\tilde{t}_{ij}^*, \tilde{0}_{ij})]_{i=1,2,\dots,l,j=1,2,\dots,m},$$

$$(4.20) \quad D_U = \begin{bmatrix} d(\tilde{t}'_{11}^*, \tilde{0}_{11}) & d(\tilde{t}'_{12}^*, \tilde{0}_{12}) & \cdot & \cdot & d(\tilde{t}'_{1m}^*, \tilde{0}_{1m}) \\ d(\tilde{t}'_{21}^*, \tilde{0}_{21}) & d(\tilde{t}'_{22}^*, \tilde{0}_{22}) & \cdot & \cdot & d(\tilde{t}'_{2m}^*, \tilde{0}_{2m}) \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ d(\tilde{t}'_{l1}^*, \tilde{0}_{l1}) & d(\tilde{t}'_{l2}^*, \tilde{0}_{l2}) & \cdot & \cdot & d(\tilde{t}'_{lm}^*, \tilde{0}_{lm}) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= [d(\tilde{t}'_{ij}^*, \tilde{0}_{ij})]_{i=1,2,\dots,l,j=1,2,\dots,m},$$

where \tilde{t}_{ij}^* and \tilde{t}'_{ij}^* are given by (4.17) and (4.18) and for $\tilde{0}_k = [(0, 0, 0); k; 1] \in V_p(k)$, $d(\tilde{t}_{ij}^*, \tilde{0}_{ij})$ and $d(\tilde{t}'_{ij}^*, \tilde{0}_{ij})$ can be obtained using Property 4.

Property 5. Let D_L^* and D_U^* denote the row normalized forms of D_L and D_U respectively and $D^* = \frac{1}{2}(D_L^* + D_U^*) = [d_{ij}^*]_{i=1,2,\dots,l,j=1,2,\dots,m}$. If $\max_{1 \leq h \leq m} d_{ih}^* = d_{ij}^*$ then patient P_i 's diagnosis can be given as d_j .

5. AN ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE

We apply our approach to the example of Yao and Yao [9] to illustrate the calculations based on the present model and to compare the results of fuzzy model with vague set theoretic model.

Let S, D, P denote sets of symptoms, diseases and patients respectively.

$$S = \{S_1(\text{headache}), S_2(\text{fever}), S_3(\text{phlegm}),\},$$

$$D = \{D_1(\text{cold}), D_2(\text{pulmonary tuberculosis}), D_3(\text{pertussis}), D_4(\text{pneumonia})\},$$

$$P = \{P_1, P_2\}.$$

Thus $n = 3, m = 4, l = 2$. Let $N = 50$ be the number of past patients on whom the statistical estimation is based. Relations \tilde{Q} and \tilde{R} given on page 357 of [9] are equivalent to \tilde{A}_L and \tilde{R}_L given below in this example:

$$\tilde{A}_L = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9 & 0.9 & 0.9 \\ 0.5 & 0.2 & 0.0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{R}_L = \begin{bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.2 & 0.1 & 0.3 \\ 0.3 & 0.4 & 0.2 & 0.1 \\ 0.1 & 0.6 & 0.1 & 0.2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

We use following non-membership relation between patients and symptoms based on physician knowledge

$$\tilde{A}_N = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0 & 0.1 & 0.1 \\ 0.3 & 0.7 & 0.8 \end{bmatrix}.$$

From \tilde{A}_N , following upper membership relation is obtained.

$$\tilde{A}_U = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0 & 0.9 & 0.9 \\ 0.7 & 0.3 & 0.2 \end{bmatrix}$$

5.1. Application of Method I. In the application of vague sets instead of fuzzy sets, it is essential to determine the non-membership relation \tilde{R}_N between symptoms and diseases. For this purpose we need the values of N'_{ij} that can be determined only if N_{ij} is known. Preserving the statistical values of \tilde{R} given in [9], we assume following values for N_{ij} , $i = 1, \dots, 3$, and $j = 1, \dots, 4$

$$\begin{aligned} N_{11} &= 12; N_{12} = 6; N_{13} = 3; N_{14} = 9, \\ N_{21} &= 6; N_{22} = 8; N_{23} = 4; N_{24} = 2, \\ N_{31} &= 4; N_{32} = 24; N_{33} = 4; N_{34} = 8. \end{aligned}$$

Using statistical analysis of section 4.1, relations \tilde{R}_N and \tilde{R}_U are obtained

$$\tilde{R}_N = \begin{bmatrix} 0.17 & 0.53 & 0.13 & 0.17 \\ 0.23 & 0.43 & 0.10 & 0.24 \\ 0.36 & 0.28 & 0.14 & 0.22 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{R}_U = \begin{bmatrix} 0.83 & 0.47 & 0.87 & 0.83 \\ 0.77 & 0.57 & 0.90 & 0.76 \\ 0.64 & 0.72 & 0.86 & 0.78 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using compositional rule of inference given in equation (4.5) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}_L &= \tilde{A}_L \circ \tilde{R}_L = \begin{bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.6 & 0.2 & 0.3 \\ 0.4 & 0.2 & 0.2 & 0.3 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \tilde{T}_U &= \tilde{A}_U \circ \tilde{R}_U = \begin{bmatrix} 0.83 & 0.72 & 0.90 & 0.83 \\ 0.70 & 0.47 & 0.70 & 0.70 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

Normalizing \tilde{T}_L and \tilde{T}_U , we get the following matrices

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}_L^* &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.2667 & 0.4000 & 0.1333 & 0.2000 \\ 0.3636 & 0.1818 & 0.1818 & 0.2727 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \tilde{T}_U^* &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.2530 & 0.2195 & 0.2744 & 0.2530 \\ 0.2724 & 0.1829 & 0.2724 & 0.2724 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

Using averaging operation between \tilde{T}_L^* and \tilde{T}_U^* to get a single relation \tilde{T}^* :

$$(5.1) \quad \tilde{T}^* = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2598 & 0.3098 & 0.2039 & 0.2265 \\ 0.3180 & 0.1823 & 0.2271 & 0.2726 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using (5.1) with probability distribution rule, the expected percentage of presence of disease in the two patients can be estimated as:

$$(5.2) \quad \begin{aligned} &\text{Patient } P_1 : D_1 \text{ is } 25.98\%; D_2 \text{ is } 30.98\%; D_3 \text{ is } 20.39\%; D_4 \text{ is } 22.65\%, \\ &\text{Patient } P_2 : D_1 \text{ is } 31.80\%; D_2 \text{ is } 18.23\%; D_3 \text{ is } 22.71\%; D_4 \text{ is } 27.26\%. \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious from (5.2) that the diagnosis for the patient P_1 is D_2 and P_2 it is D_1 .

If we use the compositional rule of inference (4.6) and follow the same procedure as in (5.1) we get following:

$$(5.3) \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{T}_L &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.72 & 1.0 & 0.36 & 0.54 \\ 0.26 & 0.18 & 0.09 & 0.17 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \tilde{T}_U &= \begin{bmatrix} 1.00 & 1.00 & 1.00 & 1.00 \\ 0.94 & 0.64 & 1.00 & 0.97 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \tilde{T}_L^* &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.2748 & 0.3817 & 0.1374 & 0.2061 \\ 0.3714 & 0.2571 & 0.1286 & 0.2429 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \tilde{T}_U^* &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.2500 & 0.2500 & 0.2500 & 0.2500 \\ 0.2649 & 0.1814 & 0.2818 & 0.2719 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \tilde{T}^* &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.2624 & 0.3158 & 0.1937 & 0.2281 \\ 0.3181 & 0.2193 & 0.2052 & 0.2574 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

Using probability distribution rule in (5.3), the expected percentage of presence of disease in the two patients can be estimated as:

$$(5.4) \quad \begin{aligned} &\text{Patient } P_1 : D_1 \text{ is } 26.24\%; D_2 \text{ is } 31.58\%; D_3 \text{ is } 19.37\%; D_4 \text{ is } 22.81\%, \\ &\text{Patient } P_2 : D_1 \text{ is } 31.81\%; D_2 \text{ is } 21.93\%; D_3 \text{ is } 20.52\%; D_4 \text{ is } 25.74\%. \end{aligned}$$

It can be observed from (5.4) that the diagnosis for the patient P_1 is D_2 and for P_2 it is D_1 .

5.2. Application of Method II.. Using equations (4.13) – (4.16) we get T_L^* and T_U^* as following:

$$T_L^* = \begin{bmatrix} t_{11}^* & t_{12}^* & t_{13}^* & t_{14}^* \\ t_{21}^* & t_{22}^* & t_{23}^* & t_{24}^* \end{bmatrix}, \quad T_U^* = \begin{bmatrix} t'_{11}^* & t'_{12}^* & t'_{13}^* & t'_{14}^* \\ t'_{21}^* & t'_{22}^* & t'_{23}^* & t'_{24}^* \end{bmatrix}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} t_{11}^* &= [(0.17, 0.72, 1.27); k; 1]; & t_{12}^* &= [(0.48, 1.08, 1.68); k; 1]; \\ t_{13}^* &= [(-0.08, 0.36, 0.80); k; 1]; & t_{14}^* &= [(0.04, 0.54, 1.04); k; 1]; \\ t_{21}^* &= [(0.09, 0.26, 0.43); k; 1]; & t_{22}^* &= [(0.03, 0.18, 0.33); k; 1]; \\ t_{23}^* &= [(-0.03, 0.09, 0.21); k; 1]; & t_{24}^* &= [(0.03, 0.17, 0.31); k; 1]. \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} t'_{11} &= [(1.70, 2.10, 2.50); k; 1]; & t'_{12} &= [(1.18, 1.63, 2.08); k; 1]; \\ t'_{13} &= [(2.15, 2.45, 2.76); k; 1]; & t'_{14} &= [(1.84, 2.22, 2.59); k; 1]; \\ t'_{21} &= [(0.78, 0.94, 1.10); k; 1]; & t'_{22} &= [(0.45, 0.64, 0.84); k; 1]; \\ t'_{23} &= [(0.92, 1.05, 1.18); k; 1]; & t'_{24} &= [(0.81, 0.97, 1.22); k; 1]. \end{aligned}$$

Using Property 4, (4.18) and (4.19) can be expressed as following:

$$\begin{aligned} D_L &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.72 & 1.08 & 0.36 & 0.54 \\ 0.26 & 0.18 & 0.09 & 0.17 \end{bmatrix}, \\ D_U &= \begin{bmatrix} 1.93 & 2.30 & 2.10 & 2.08 \\ 1.55 & 1.81 & 1.65 & 1.60 \end{bmatrix}, \\ D_L^* &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.2666 & 0.4000 & 0.1333 & 0.2000 \\ 0.3714 & 0.2571 & 0.1285 & 0.2428 \end{bmatrix}, \\ D_U^* &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.2500 & 0.1940 & 0.2917 & 0.2642 \\ 0.2611 & 0.1778 & 0.2917 & 0.2694 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

From Property 5, the diagnostic decision can be taken with the help of the following relation:

$$(5.5) \quad D^* = \frac{1}{2}(D_L^* + D_U^*) = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2583 & 0.2970 & 0.2125 & 0.2321 \\ 0.3163 & 0.2175 & 0.2101 & 0.2561 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Using probability distribution rule in (5.5), the expected percentage of presence of disease in the two patients can be estimated as:

$$(5.6) \quad \begin{aligned} \text{Patient } P_1 : D_1 \text{ is } 25.83\%; D_2 \text{ is } 29.70\%; D_3 \text{ is } 21.25\%; D_4 \text{ is } 23.21\%, \\ \text{Patient } P_2 : D_1 \text{ is } 31.63\%; D_2 \text{ is } 21.75\%; D_3 \text{ is } 21.01\%; D_4 \text{ is } 25.61\%. \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious from (5.6) that the diagnosis for the patient P_1 is D_2 and for P_2 it is D_1 .

6. DISCUSSIONS

The diagnostic decisions of the case study are shown in (5.2), (5.4) and (5.6). Results show that the patients, P_1 and P_2 have maximum likelihood for the diseases D_2 and D_1 respectively. It will help the physician to take a decision on the diagnosis in a manner similar to the fuzzy model [9]. However, on comparing our results given in (5.2), (5.4) and (5.6) with the corresponding results (1.1), (1.2) and (2) [9, page 358] respectively, it is observed that the possibility margin in favour of each of the four diseases for the two patients P_1 and P_2 have meaningful changes. In [9], the difference in the possibility margin for the diagnosis D_2 in patient P_1 (against the nearest disease D_1) and the diagnosis D_1 in patient P_2 (against the nearest disease D_4) range about 11–13% and 9–13% respectively. In our analysis, which is based on the favourable and unfavourable evidence separately, the margin is narrowed to about 4–5% and 4–6% respectively. This would help the consultant physician to consider it as the first line of treatment. Close observation of patient's response to this line of treatment would enable the physician to gather some more evidence. Thus he would be able to confirm the diagnostic decision between the two close diseases. In real life applications, the diagnosis based on our approach will prove very useful to locate the exact disease.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The diagnosis of disease in a patient is based on symptom-disease and patient symptom relationship. A single symptom may be indicative of more than one disease and many diseases on a single patient may disrupt the expected symptom pattern. A good decision model must take into account the favourable and unfavourable evidence separately, to cover up the vagueness in the symptom disease relationship and the lack of specificity in patient-symptom observations. It must also be ready to accept some hidden or unobserved uncertainties. A patient may have observed some symptoms like cough, fever, and chest pain but he might not have observed or given importance to swelling in axilla (armpit). In such situations, μ_x is not equal to $1 - \nu_x$. It would rather satisfy the inequality $\mu_x + \nu_x < 1$. Hence it will be useful to identify meaningful lower and upper bounds for the membership grades, to make the diagnostic decision more credible. This work has introduced the concept of triangular vague numbers to extend the diagnostic decision model of Yao and Yao [9]. Our approach for decision making is not

only based on independent considerations for favourable and unfavourable evidence but also leaves a room for the unknown part. This model may have a little more computational demand as compared to [9] but it handles the decision making with more reality and credibility. Use of computer software based on this model may remove the disadvantage of computational demand.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the Referee for his useful comments and constructive suggestions to improve the quality of the paper. Second author is also thankful to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, India for providing him financial assistance to pursue research.

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